

Ethical issues of COVID-19 – the emerging Big Five

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Summary

From an ethical perspective, the pandemic is like a prism: it helps us see the spectrum of issues clearly and distinctly. In our contribution we shall outline what we consider top ethics concerns, grouped around five moral and societal core values: autonomy, privacy, equity, proportionality and trust. We then proceed to probe these concerns a bit further with some examples around vaccination of health care professionals, contact tracing, global access to vaccines, lockdowns, and crisis communication. We are quite aware that the dynamic, cross-sectoral, multilevel impact of both the pandemic and the measures taken to contain it is too complex to be captured by a simple short list of ethical issues. This is a huge challenge for healthcare leaders and healthcare professionals. To keep a clear and current overview of this moving target, we propose a value-based checklist, centered around five core moral values which are unlikely to change over time, that will allow healthcare leaders to systematically analyze ethical issues arising in their institutions. Each section of the checklist (centered around one of the core values) includes a dynamic presentation of emerging topics (in the form of a word cloud or any other suitable format) that can and will change, generated with a natural language processing (NLP) approach, using an open-source topic tracking algorithm as a means of tackling the exploding volume of literature on bioethics and COVID-19, allowing for quick overview of thematic priorities.

The pandemics as a prism for ethical issues

For over two years the COVID pandemic has taken center stage, pretty much anywhere around the world. Not only has it caused death and suffering, but it has also absorbed our energy and attention. Other global issues such as climate change or the privatization of space have gone almost unnoticed. For ethics, the pandemic is like a prism: it helps us see the spectrum of issues clearly and distinctly. In the following we outline what we consider top ethics issues, grouped around five moral and societal core values, and probe them a bit further with some examples.

The pandemic affects not only our physical but also our mental and social wellbeing. It affects individuals, groups and the global community. It has triggered the rapid development and accelerated the deployment of new technologies, many of which involve digital and AI components such as tracing apps and triaging algorithms. We are quite aware that the dynamic, cross-sectoral, multilevel impact of both the pandemic and the measures taken to contain it is too complex to be captured by a simple short list of ethical issues. Our contribution can only be a teaser for a deeper dive into the plethora of Covid-19-related moral questions.

This is why we end this paper with a value-based checklist that allows healthcare leaders to systematically analyze ethical issues arising in their institutions. In addition, we suggest an open-source digital topic tracker as a means of tackling the exploding volume of literature in bioethics, allowing for quick overview of thematic priorities and gaps in the existing literature.

The Big Five: ethical issues of COVID-19

1. The role of autonomy, individual rights and freedom in a pandemic

Citizens around the globe have been subjected to serious restrictions of their liberties: Quarantine requirements, closed borders and curfews have limited our ability to move freely; events and gatherings including political demonstrations have been banned; we have not been able to visit family members even when they were seriously sick or dying; we have been required to reveal personal information, for instance when going to a restaurant, to enable contact tracing; we have been required to wear masks, many have not been able to attend schools or go to work (Secretary General of the Council of Europe 2020b; 2020a) Vaccine mandates have been discussed, and in some countries applied (Druml and Czech 2022); and nudging strategies like limiting access to public spaces or facilities to vaccinated individuals have been enforced, not without controversy (Spitale, Biller-Andorno, and Germani 2022).

All of this has happened, of course, for good reason. Still, there is some uneasiness around the sudden – albeit temporary – loss of personal liberties that had been taken for granted by citizens in many countries. Careful legitimation of restrictions as subsidiary to individual responsibility and restoration of civil liberties as soon as possible will be important from an ethical and human rights perspective (Studdert and Hall 2020; Flood et al. 2020).

A current example of weighing individual freedom and autonomous choice against public health concerns vaccination against Covid-19. Whereas the speed with which vaccines have been developed surpassed most people's expectations, there is surprisingly widespread hesitancy to get vaccinated (Spitale, Biller-Andorno, and Germani 2022; Barello et al. 2020; Peretti-Watel et al. 2020; Dror et al. 2020). For some, this hesitancy may be rooted in a principle anti-vaxx stance, others may be skeptical because of the great speed with which vaccines were tested and approved (Murphy et al. 2021; Puri et al. 2020; Wouters et al. 2021). Whereas an argument can already be made for every citizen to carry a responsibility to contribute to herd immunity, matters get even more acute in the case of health care workers. Interestingly, it is this group who is not only particularly exposed but also at risk of spreading the disease among vulnerable patients that seems to be in large parts unwilling to receive the vaccine (Kirzinger et al. 2021). There is a spectrum of possible responses from acceptance of refusals to nudging to indirect pressure (e.g. vaccination requirement for certain activities) to compulsory vaccinations. Finding the least invasive measure that is still effective enough to protect the health patients will be a task that needs to be tackled in the context of national regulations, considering a range of empirical factors, including the urgency of the intervention, the availability of alternatives, and likely reactions.

2. Privacy vs. efficient and effective pandemic management

A second set of ethical issues revolves around privacy, another core value in liberal democracies. The availability of data is key to fight a pandemic. Very different kinds of data can be helpful to understand the impact of the pandemic and the measures taken to contain it on population groups (Gasser et al. 2020). Among those data are, for instance, proximity and contact tracing, flow modelling and quarantine compliance. Proximity and contact tracing is a way of trying to follow and break infection chains. Tracing apps were developed in many countries, requiring difficult trade-offs between effectiveness and data protection and thorough ponderation on potential risks (repurposing of the tracing systems or of the data after the pandemic, data access, possibilities of re-identification using collateral datasets, security vulnerabilities, and (im)possibility to withdraw consent and erase personal data) (Ahmed et al. 2020; Braithwaite et al. 2020). But again, voluntary uptake of the apps was not overwhelming in many countries (Walrave, Waeterloos, and Ponnet 2020; Munzert et al. 2021; Jonker et al. 2020). And indeed, the voluntary use of a tracking device presupposes significant trust not only in the technology but in the government and other players who may access the data. This trust might be put at risk if choice architecture is used to make people use such tools (e.g. through opt-out schemes) against their conviction.

Ethical questions such as “Should police enter a building against residents’ will if they suspect a party with more than the permitted number of participants?” can also emerge in low-tech settings. However, digitalization has greatly enhanced the potential for effective surveillance, for instance using IoT devices for live tracking, employing personal movement data to model potential disease activity, tasking AI applications with detection of COVID-19 from chest imaging (Ting et al. 2020; Budd et al. 2020), or even using robotic dogs to enforce social distancing (Nalewicki 2020). In analogy to restriction of autonomy and individual freedom, privacy intrusions need to be very carefully justified, transparently communicated, secured against abuse and abolished as soon as no longer required. Finally, as emerged from a recent study on no-green-pass groups, a clear communication on the scope, duration, and limitation of measures that compress the space of individual privacy could be a crucial factor to improve the uptake of these measures (Spitale, Biller-Andorno, and Germani 2022).

3. Equity, fairness and solidarity under conditions of resource scarcity

From an ethical point of view, it seems fairly straightforward that ending a pandemic requires global cooperation and that scarce resources should be allocated according to need. Yet equitable distribution of goods such as intensive care beds or vaccines has proven a highly complex issue (Holzer et al. 2021). Over the past year, numerous guidelines have been developed that define allocation criteria and procedural rules (Jöbges et al. 2020). Key considerations that have emerged relate to maximizing utility, non-discrimination, fairness and protection of vulnerable groups.

Recent struggles regarding the distribution of still scarce vaccines show that implementation of seemingly simple rules and criteria is not easy in real life. Although an international mechanism for the global distribution of vaccines has been established (CEPI et al. 2020; COVAX 2020), governments are securing supplies through bilateral agreements with pharmaceutical companies. The stock of some countries by far exceeding their need, whereas others have not even been able to start vaccination programs due to a lack of vaccines (Wouters et al. 2021; CEPI 2020; Khamsi 2020). Whereas moral consensus can easily be reached that hoarding is not defensible in the face of resource scarcity, there is a lively

ongoing debate between nationalist and cosmopolitan views. A further level of complexity is added by the fact that not all vaccines are equally safe, effective and easy to transport and store. The debate is fueled by the expectation that vaccinated individuals or societies will have restrictions lifted and go back to normal more quickly than those not protected by a vaccine. Given the tremendous societal and economic impact of measures such as closed shops and travel restrictions, the speed of vaccination carries is highly significant for many countries.

4. Proportionality of measures: legitimation and procedures

Governments struggle with the giant task of how to maneuver best through the crisis. There are different perspectives on how much of a top-down approach is needed, how much controversy can be afforded and to what extent citizens should be involved in evaluating and prioritizing options. It has become clear, however, that building resilience involves a multilevel network of interconnected drivers and health, social, economic and environmental systems and – at least in democratic societies – needs to rely on participation, communication, coordination, learning and polycentricity as governance principles (Antulov-Fantulin et al. 2021).

How proportionality is to be established in concrete cases – e.g. such as shutting down hotels based on a certain incidence level – is a question that currently intensely debated among legal scholars. Although the issue is disputed (Prati and Mancini 2021), there are voices from within the academic community in different countries who question the proportionality of protracted lockdowns, which might eventually cause, so the argument, comparable or even more damage to populations than the pandemic would have had (Luo et al. 2020; Salari et al. 2020; Vindegaard and Benros 2020). How proportionality should be established, by whom, according to which criteria and procedure is currently a field of contention. In bioethics, there is a clear distinction between the descriptive and normative level, i.e., it is not given that ‘what people believe’ is per se ‘the right thing to do’. Nevertheless, empirical data collected through citizen science approaches can greatly contribute to informing this debate with contextual information, e.g., on acceptability thresholds.

5. Trust and trustworthiness

The pandemic and its management have put high demands on public trust. Particularly in the early phase, little evidence was available on crucial matters such as infection rate, available treatment, effective preventive measures, case fatality rate or risk factors. The paucity of high-quality evidence contrasted with the abundance of mis- and disinformation, especially on social media (Gallotti et al. 2020; WHO 2020; 2020). At the same time, the pandemic and subsequent public health measures have severely affected the lives of most people around the globe. Crisis communication therefore played a key role in maintaining trust and enhancing the likelihood of compliance with hygiene and other rules.

Communication, however, has tended to be quite directive and unilateral. Whereas this may have been appropriate in the early phase of the pandemic, a more bidirectional approach is needed in the longer run. Not only do citizens need to know what health authorities want them to do – health authorities also need to know how citizens perceive the situation, how they react emotionally, how they are likely going to behave and what stance they take on

moral questions such as the allocation of scarce vaccines. Such a nuanced, comprehensive understanding is necessary to tailor information and policy responses. Again, digitalization provides excellent opportunities to build interactive platforms that allow for real-time analyses (Spitale et al. 2021).

Trust, however, is only a good if it is justified. Authorities should therefore not only try to obtain citizens' trust but to also deserve it as trustworthy institutions doing their best at correctly informing, devising appropriate measures that take into account what parts of the population will be affected and how, and ensuring conflicts of interest do not get in the way of the overall aim of reducing the harm caused by the pandemic – either directly, through its health impact, or indirectly, through measures taken to contain it. An important challenge for authorities relates to the question of how to deal with radical dissenters who might influence others with unfounded conspiracy theories and open opposition to public health measures. Although certain measures might be justified to maintain public order, oppressing diversity of opinion through overreaching censorship might encourage societal polarization. Prudent judgement will be in place to respect freedom of expression without compromising social stability.

[A Covid-19 value-based ethics checklist](#)

Although we are confident that we have captured key values and moral tensions exemplified by concrete examples we do see some added value in systematically looking at the published international literature (in English) to get a sense of where priorities have emerged, but also to investigate which topics may have received less attention. Our goal is to complement the theoretical reflection based on which we developed the Big Five with a checklist of concrete issues in which the Big Five play a pivotal role. As healthcare leaders need to keep abreast of their COVID-19 management, and issues have become so manifold, it is important to keep an overview. Therefore, we propose an up-to-date analysis of current issues structured around the Big Five, generated through an innovative digital tool.

This approach has an important added value: this analysis can be rapidly and dynamically updated with a re-run and re-analysis of the same queries, a crucial feature when dealing with fast-paced situations subject to rapid evolution – as proven by the sheer number of papers captured by our queries.

[The TopicTracker – navigating through the flood](#)

For this purpose, we have developed a digital tool to search, download and explore PubMed entries. The TopicTracker is written in Python and structured in a collection of three Jupyter notebooks in order to provide together the code and its explanation. The first notebook allows to build PubMed queries, download entries, parse them, and save the results. The output of the first notebook can be explored with the second and third notebooks of this collection. The second notebook allows to perform simple NLP analysis on the trends of entities (keywords, MeSH terms, authors, journals, lemmas in title/abstract, amount of COI statements, lemma trends in COI statements). The third notebook allows fully interactive exploration of the datasets preprocessed with the second notebook. The whole package is

available through the Zenodo repository under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (Spitale and Biller-Andorno 2021).

Strategy

To determine the core areas of discussion about the interplay between the Big Five and the COVID-19 pandemic, we ran a set of five queries (detailed in Multimedia Appendix 1) in the TopicTracker. Each query collects articles regarding COVID-19 and one of the Big Five, published between 2019 and March 2022. Medline files resulting from the queries and TopicTracker logs are available for further research (Multimedia Appendix 2).

In order to develop a dynamic checklist, we focused our analysis on keywords and MeSH terms. To correct for the different number of publications per year (especially keeping in mind that the query has been run in March 2022) we normalized all the frequencies dividing the count per year by the number of articles published in the same year captured by the query. Keywords and MeSH terms cannot be duplicated, so they can be understood as percentages (100% = every article uses that keyword/MeSH term).

Results

Although we consider all the Big Five of equal importance, some topics appear to be more discussed than others, suggesting that in some specific areas further research is needed, especially on proportionality and on privacy. Results are reported in Table 1. Detailed output (normalized dataframes of keywords and MeSH terms, word clouds and plots of the top 5 entities in each dataframe) is provided for further analysis (multimedia Appendix 3).

Query	Papers
The role of autonomy, rights and freedom in a pandemic	2215
Privacy vs. efficient and effective pandemic management	895
Equity, fairness and solidarity under conditions of resource scarcity	2659
Proportionality of measures: legitimation and procedures	55
Trust and trustworthiness	2311

Table 1. Detailed results of the five 'big five' queries

The role of autonomy, rights and freedom in a pandemic

Scholarly discourse on autonomy, rights and freedom focuses mostly on recognizing and incorporating human rights when developing or deploying public health measures, namely quarantine and lockdown. Other areas in which autonomy plays a central role appear to be telemedicine, surveillance systems, and vaccines. Normalized MeSH terms provide good methodological hints, suggesting that empirical work in this area is primarily conducted with surveys, questionnaires, and qualitative approaches.

Figure 5. Word cloud of the top 50 keywords in the 5th query

Covid 19: a catastrophe and a chance to learn

One day in the hopefully not too distant future we will be looking back at the pandemic and try to understand how well we performed. This assessment should not be limited to parameters such as excess mortality, but also include questions such “How well did we handle ethical issues that arose?”, “How well did we protect and care for our citizens, in particular the vulnerable and underprivileged?”, “Did we manage to strengthen our democracies and the confidence of our citizens?” or “Have we understood how we can build resilient institutions and societies that can withstand crises?”. This questioning will have a fundamental value, not only as a retrospective evaluation but most importantly as a prospective set of lessons to keep in mind not to be unprepared for future crises.

Tackling the pandemic requires the cooperation of many actors – healthcare institutions, governments, citizens, international organizations, companies and others. Working towards a joint understanding of who carries what responsibility to uphold our ethical core values and to resolve unavoidable moral tension and disagreement will help us improve our pandemic preparedness so we can look confidently ahead. Smart digital tools can support leaders and decision-makers in keeping track of emerging ethical issues even when times become particularly challenging.

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